

iQonic

Innovative strategies, sensing and process chains for increased
Quality, re-configurability, and recyclability of Manufacturing
Optoelectronics

Deliverable

D3.3 Assembly Process Chain Model

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY / ABSTRACT

This report (D3.3 Assembly Process Chain Model) deals with the definition of the photonics assembly process chain, ranging from components manufacturing to system integration. Based on this process chain main processes and process interfaces are derived and described, which the iQonic architecture is based on. Main building blocks of the iQonic architecture then are discussed regarding their general layout, from the overall process chain of view.

SCOPE

The scope of this deliverable is to provide an understanding how the process chain for the manufacturing of photonics components and systems that drives the iQonic architecture and its individual building blocks.

ABBREVIATIONS

ADJ	Adjust
DIA	Diagnose
PRD	Predict
PRV	Prevent
DET	Detect
SUS	Sustain
MAN	Manage
RED	Redesign
LED	Light emitting Diode
ZDM	Zero-Defect Manufacturing
VOC	Volatile Organic Compounds
RAMI 4.0	Reference Architectural Model Industrie 4.0
IoT	Internet of Things
IIoT	Industrial Internet Of Things
OPC-UA	Open Platform Communications-Unified Architecture
MQTT	MQ Telemetry Transport
LAN	Local Area network
QoS	Quality-of-Service
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
CPS	Cyber-Physical System
DSS	Decision Support System
RSC	Reverse Supply Chain
PdM	Predictive Maintenance
EvMod	Event Modeler
SFCM	Shop Floor Communication Middleware
MLCM	Machine-Level Communication Middleware
HLCM	Higher-Level Communication Middleware
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
MES	Machine Execution System

I Introduction

Industrial manufacturing of optics evolved from the midst of 19th century (based on inventions by Zeiss, Abbe and Schott about manufacturing methodologies, scientific descriptions of optical system performances, and material developments) to nowadays production. Still optics and photonics manufacturing pose, in contrast to other industries, specific requirements such as precision, stability, cleanliness and complex assembly procedures. Rapid growing usage of new types of light sources (lasers, semiconductor based LED) drive the term of “photonics” that are made of active and passive optical and electro-optical components. Applications for photonics can in principle be divided into illumination (apply light onto something) or imaging (collect light for gaining information) applications.

Optics and photonics are cross-cutting technologies, they can be found in applications that arise from markets such as automotive, medical technologies, information and security, consumer goods, and scientific instrumentation. But, optics and photonics are also used in manufacturing technologies for various markets, e.g. for direct material processing using photons (e.g. laser ablation or lithography) or for sensing technologies to characterize manufacturing quality. This illustrates, that optics and photonics is a technology that has one of the broadest scopes and applications nowadays, which is directly also influencing the assembly process chain.

Figure 1: The optics and photonics assembly chain

The optics and photonics assembly chain, as depicted in Figure 1, is composed of many process steps, from the manufacturing and preparation of components for the assembly process, via handling, alignment and finally bonding of component in the photonic system or sub-systems, followed by its post inspection and characterization. The processes of the assembly chain are often nested, and during a complex and multi-step manufacturing, assembly and integration process chain, various sources of component and system performance information, errors and defects result in yield ratios that are comparably low, in comparison to other industry sectors. A further challenge is that volumes in photonics production range from small to medium, only in a few applications volumes higher than 10.000 p.a are reached. Low production volumes make it difficult to track singular defects, their origins and impact onto the final photonic system quality.

The iQonic architecture makes use of a sensorial network within the photonics manufacturing and assembly process chain that is acquiring production and defect relevant data. This data represents descriptors for main sources of a photonic system’s quality and defects, in particular contamination and surface damages, as well as component irregularities, such as geometry deviations. This real-time data, in conjunction with historic data from previous process flows, is transferred into a software based manufacturing and assembly model, based on artificial intelligence and decision support. It will allow for i) error compensation during the complete manufacturing chain, ii) early malfunction detection on the component and system level, and iii) component-rework and re-assessment.

1.1 Objectives

The main objective of the assembly process chain model is to provide information about individual photonics assembly processes, their input and output data and their interfaces, in order to:

- Derive common input and output data,
- Mention also more uncommon input and output data,
- Provide insight about general data structure of processes.

1.2 Relationship with other Work Packages

Figure 2: WP relationship diagram

The present document is closely affiliated with the following work packages and tasks (Figure 1):

WP2 - Requirements and Conceptual Process Chain Design

- T2.1 – Consolidation of user requirements
- T2.3 – Design and architecture of the process chain and strategies
- T2.4 – Use case design

WP3 - Opto-Electrical System Design for Assembly and Disassembly

- T3.3 – Overall process chain for producing opto-electrical parts based on functionalities

WP4 - Data management, sensor, and processes design and setup

- T4.1 – Multisensorial data acquisition network for manufacturing opto-electrical parts

1.3 Document Structure

This document is structured in the following way:

- Chapter 1 contains an **Introduction** of the deliverable scope and structure. It provides an overview of the role of this task along with its relationships with related work packages.
- Chapter 2 presents the **Problem Statement** concerning this document and provides the basic concept behind this along with the assembly process chain definition. The requirements and specifications are presented in this chapter as well.
- Chapter 3 provides the **typical interface** descriptions. Due to the multiphysics nature of photonics components and systems this collection of interfaces can only be exemplary.
- Finally, Chapter 4 presents the **Conclusions** and the next actions related to task T3.5.

2 Problem Statement

2.1 Assembly Process Chain

The photonics assembly chain, as depicted in Figure 1 already, is in principle comparable to classical assembly process chains that can also be found in other industries, in particular those that have to rely onto precision (alignment) and cleanliness (preparation). The difference in photonics is the type of components that are processed during assembly, and the approaches to assembly processes. Regarding photonics components and systems, the following specific boundary conditions have to be considered:

- Materials
 - o Photonics use probably the broadest variability of materials. Components are made of glass, polymer, metal, ceramics, glass ceramics.
 - o Additional materials are used e.g. for coatings, for bonding (glue), for the manufacturing itself (abrasives for grinding) and so on.
 - o The materials have different material parameters, those range e.g. from brittle (glass) to very soft (some crystals) materials.
- Geometries
 - o Geometrical variability in photonics is also broad, ranging from micro-optics with dimensions <1 mm to components with infinitive aspect ratios (glass fibers) to macroscopical components (that can have, due to the density of glass, high mass).
- Sensitivity
 - o Next to material properties like brittleness or softness of bulk materials and coatings, that are e.g. relevant for handling procedures, in opto-electronics and photonics also electro-optical components like optical semiconductor chips for lasers, LED and photodiodes, are used. Those are sensitive versus electrostatic discharge, a phenomenon that has to be addressed during assembly cautiously.

Defects of optics and photonics components consequently are caused by abnormalities regarding the mentioned boundary conditions. Typical examples are:

- Geometrical deviations that affect refractive or diffractive optical performance,
- Impurities (bulk volume defects such as blurs and voids, or surface defects such as scratches or coating inhomogeneities) that also affect refractive, diffractive or reflective optical performance,
- Contaminations on optical surfaces (e.g. particles or volatile organic compounds) that affect transmission and reflection.

Nevertheless, not every defect results in a non-conformant system performance. Thus the assembly process chain must take components information into account and provide those, which is the goal if the iQonic project.

Figure 3: The photonics assembly process chain and its interface

The hardware based process chain that is processing components towards complete systems is controlled by process control software. The control realizes flow schemes and parameters for the individual processes. It is the state of the art already, that decision making is supported. iQonic now is aiming for a sensor network that generates data from the whole photonics assembly process chain that allows for a process control that does not only follow fixed process schemes, but that also takes historical data into account and that reacts “live” from actual events within the process chain.

Figure 4: iQonic’s generic software architecture

The generic architecture, as depicted in Figure 4, will be established in detail within the project by means of various building blocks, as depicted in Figure 5.

Figure 5: The overall iQonic s/w architecture

Note that the iQonic architecture contains various software building blocks that all are able to use data from assembly process and to influence parameters of assembly processes, ranging from the actually assembled photonic product towards future products and even reworked components and systems. Details for what individual building blocks can do are to be found in the deliverable D2.3.

2.2 Assembly Processes

Taking a closer look at the individual photonics assembly processes, in the following it shall be described which are in- and output items for each process and what is the data that flows in and out.

a) Preparation

Preparation of components in optics and photonics covers various aspects. The manufacturing of the component itself shall not be considered "preparation" here, but the singularization of components from substrate level (e.g. wafer sawing of individual semiconductor chips from a wafer) can be considered as a first step. Before and/ or after incoming inspection takes place, to find non-conformancies in the components. Cleaning is another important part of preparation, there are dry and wet technologies available, depending on the type of contamination and the sensitivity/ material of the components. Throughout cleaning inspection of the cleanliness state is carried out as one of most important preparation step. Storing the components in a magazine, providing shelter from contamination and electrostatic discharge, as well as providing a basic geometrical orientation and position for the sub-sequent handling process, conclude the preparation.

Figure 6: Preparation and feeding of optics and photonics components

b) Handling

Handling of optics and photonics components has to consider material properties, as there is typically a mechanical contact between the tool (gripper) and the component, which might damage the surface of the component. Another important measure is that handling has to be conducted until the end of the sub-sequent alignment and bonding processes, thus handling shall not interfere with those. An example is that active alignment requires that specific optical surfaces and apertures have to stay accessible throughout the assembly process chain and thus shall not be covered or obstructed by the handling tool. Also, in case of clamping or

glueing, the handling tool shall not prevent from applying respective tools or media. This can become challenging in particular for miniaturized component.

The handling force itself needs to be designed in a way that it allows for secure handling with respect to all occurring forces during assembly (mass, acceleration, bonding forces etc.), while in the same time the handling force shall not introduce over-the-limit mechanical stress and deformation. The latter is in particular critical for the active alignment of components, as handling forces might tamper the desired, optimum alignment result. Handling also covers the transfer from the magazine (see "preparation") to the actual assembly position, where specific acceleration forces can occur that have to be compensated by the handling tool. Often a different positioning tool is used here, as the required accuracy is at least an order of magnitude less than during alignment itself, while in contrast large distances between the magazine and the assembly position have to be covered.

Figure 7: Handling of optics and photonics components

c) Alignment

The alignment process for optics and photonics components is one of the most crucial and specific tasks. Very often the components have to be aligned in up to all six degrees of freedom, at an accuracy in the micron / arcsec range. Alignment in photonics is carried out in an open-loop (passive) or closed-loop (active) way. For passive alignment technologies such as mechanical contact of components at hard stops are used to determine the component's position, which requires additional sensors to determine the contacts, while the accuracy is typically limited to 20..50 microns. Active alignment, in contrast, makes use of a broad variability of measurement technologies that either determine the geometrical position of the component in the six DOF directly, or that measure optical functionality, which is an indirect representation of the component's position and properties - both together determine it optical performance, the key figure of merit for alignment.

The post-bond alignment quality and performance in photonics is known to be influenced by the following bonding process. It is very common to collect statistical data that allows for deriving systematic errors that occur during bonding and that can be pre-compensated for during alignment.

Figure 8: Alignment of optics and photonics components

d) Bonding

Laser-soldered Fiber in V-Groove

Figure 9: Alignment of optics and photonics components

The fixation or bonding of optics takes place by clamping, by force-fit, by media-based bonding or by a combination of those. As already mentioned the bonding process might influence the quality of the previous

alignment process. Additionally, bonding can be a source of contamination (particles from abrasive friction load in case of clamping, volatile organic compounds that are created during polymerization/ solidification of organic based glues) and damage (thermally driven processes like curing of epoxie glues or the reflow of solder might damage thermoshock-sensitive optical surfaces). But besides contamination and damage bonding can also alter the state of an optics, e.g. by introducing mechanical stress and resulting surface deformation or birefringence in the bulk material. Also bonding is relevant for the long-term stability of the photonic's system performance, as long term effects such as degradation can affect the alignment state and the performance of the optical component. Also these effects can partially be compensated for.

The quality of bonding can further be influenced by a variety of factors, in particular for technologies that use a medium as a bonding agent. There, the quality of the bonding agent (life time, shelf life etc.), parameters of the solidification process (e.g. UV wavelength and intensity for UV-polmerizing adhesives, the humidity of the environment, its oxygen content etc.) as well as the quality of the surfaces (contamination, micro-structure and roughness, chemical activation) where the bonding agent is applied on, are of relevance. These factors influence the bonding strength, but the material parameters of the bond and, consequently, its alignment stability also.

2.3 Summary for Assembly Process Objectives

The decriptions of the assembly processes can be summarized with respect to their objectives as follows, providing a basis for the interface discussion in the next chapter:

- Preparation
 - o Singularization from a (carrier) substrate
 - o Incoming inspection for contaminations and defects
 - o Cleaning of optical and bonding surfaces
 - o Geometrical orientation
 - o Protection from re-contamination after cleaning
 - o Protection from electrostatic discharge
- Handling
 - o Pick-up, fixation and release of the component to be mounted during the full assembly process chain
 - o Realizing a handling force as high as needed that compensates (including a safety margin) for the sum of all assembly (acceleration) forces that act at the same time
 - o Realizing a handling force as low as possible to avoid damage, deformation or stress application onto the components
 - o Avoid obstruction of optical apertures needed for alignment
 - o Avoid handling contamination due to friction abrasion at the contact between tool and component
- Alignment
 - o Align the component in up to six DOF at the desired position
 - o Apply open- or closed-loop feedback control for the desired position
 - o Align for a figure of merit, if multiple optimization goals for the desired position are applicable
 - o Pre-compensate for known systematic effects from bonding, regarding the final position
- Bonding
 - o Provide a suitable environment for the bonding process
 - o Apply and functionalize a bonding agent (clamp, medium/ adhesive)
 - o Minimize the bonding effect onto the alignment result
 - o Fixate the alignment result over time (long-term stability)

3 Interfaces

3.1 Generalized Assembly Process Interfaces

The assembly processes have the following interfaces:

- Input
 - The physical input of a process is the component to be assembled, as well as it's accompanying data. The latter is in particular important for process control, if the component's data describes deviations from the ideal component properties, that still make the component valid for assembly, while taking boundary conditions and specific relationship between component parameters and performance figures into account¹.
- Output
 - The physical output of a process is the processed component.
- Process Parameters
 - Direct process parameters relate to an optimum result of the process.
 - Indirect process parameters have a model-based influence onto process results.
 - Derivation of process parameters is subject to various types of models developed for the iQonic architecture, based on historic data and process sensorics
- Process data sensorics
 - Provide feedback for direct and indirect process parameters.

The following table collects typical inputs, outputs, process parameters and process data from a photonics assembly process chain. It is not meant to be a complete overview.

Table 1: Assembly process interfaces

	Preparation	Handling	Alignment	Bonding
Input	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single components - Components within substrate (e.g. on wafer level) - Components on carrier / tray 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single components - Clean components - Pre-characterized components - Pre-classified components - Components on carrier / tray 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Component within handling tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aligned component
Output	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Single components - Components on carrier - Clean components - Pre-characterized components - Pre-classified components 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Component within handling tool 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Aligned component 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonded component

¹ An example would be a deviation from the nominal focal length of a lens that would result in a different desired position of the lens in the system, while not necessarily compromising the overall performance of the system.

<p>Direct Process Parameters</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Singulation technology parameters (wafer sawing, cleaving etc.) - Cleaning recipe and conditions - Inspection recipe and framework - Storage parameters (feeding geometrical accuracy, holding force in the feeding media) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Handling force - Handling motion parameters (acceleration, velocity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alignment goal and quantitative representation - Alignment tolerances 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonding technology process parameters (e.g. dispensed volume of adhesive, UV curing intensity and time etc.) - Alignment compensation parameters (e.g. compensation movements during bonding) - Handling compensation parameters (e.g. variable/ decreasing handling force during bonding)
<p>Indirect Process Parameters</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Inspection environment (cleanliness, illumination) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Handling medium quality (e.g purity of vacuum for vacuum tools) - Quality of electrostatic discharge prevention - Safety margin for handling force - Handling environment (humidity) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Component quality - Alignment environment (temperature stability and drifts) - Positioning system resolution and stability - Measurement system resolution and accuracy 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Bonding environment parameters (humidity, oxygen content, temperature stability etc.) - Environment illumination (e.g. UV light content) - Positioning system stability, in particular during fixation (e.g. bonding agent curing) - Tool parameters for bonding tools (e.g. hours of operation for UV sources and respective degradation)
<p>Generated Process Data</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presence of components - Geometrical data (shape, surface accuracy / conformity) - Defect data (deviations from design features) - Particle contamination 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Presence of component in handling tool - (un-wanted) mechanical contact during handling 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Alignment data (measurement feedback) - Specific optical performance data based on active alignment (beam profiles etc.) - Specific optical performance data based on passive 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Post-bonding alignment data (measurement feedback) - Specific optical post-bonding performance data based on alignment (beam profiles etc.)

	- General contamination		alignment (beam profiles etc.) - Specific passive alignment data such as mechanical contact at stops or clamps	
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3.2 Use Case Discussion

The described assembly process chain is partially or completely present throughout iQonic’s use cases. Nevertheless, the use cases provide different fokii – onto components and preparation (Filar-I, ALPES), and on assemblys and integration (PRIMA, FILAR II, BRIGHTERWAVE), which shall be described in the following:

ALPES use case:

The ALPES use case focuses on the feeding of semiconductor laser chip towards a manual, tool supported assembly process. The laser chips are provided on a wafer level. The main task in the ALPES use case is to identify component defects on the wafer level, to pre-classify components based on these defects and to map the wafer that classified components can be singulated (by cleaving and individual pick-up) as the output of the preparation step.

PRIMA use case:

The main goal of the PRIMA use case is an automated assembly of multi-emitter laser diode modules, where the multi-emitters are already mounted in a housing and where the main task is to align focusing lenses in front of each emitter and to combine the individual coused beams to one common beam. The quality of the common beam is determined by the parameters of each individual emitter that is contributing to the overal beam, as well as by the component quality of each focusing lens (and beam combining element), as well as their alignment states and the bonding performance to fix the alignment state. The overall quality of each module thus is determined by a multi-parametric component and assembly process framework. The PRIMA use case is th most multi-parametric use case within iQonic and thus provides highest potential for multi-parametric optimization approaches.

FILAR-I use case:

The FILAR-I use case covers in particular component manufacturing that determines final component quality. Here specific manufacturing processes for crystalline components (such as YAG or Alexandrite), like ultrasonic drilling of a rod out of boule, disk cutting out of the rod, disc grinding, polishing and chamfering. Various manufacturing process parameters determine component features and quality, such as thickness accuracy, wedge error, chamfer cracks, and fron- / backside surface planarity, roughness, and scratches. The main output of the use case is acomponent at a specific quality. This quality is to be re-determined in the FILAR-II use case, as an input parameter.

FILAR-II use case:

The FILAR-II use case covers the bonding of a coated crystal disk to a heat sink by means of thinfilm adhesive bonding. Due to boundary conditions of the high power application, the quality of the crystal disk and the heat sink are most important, those have to be pre-determined before the assembly by means of inspection and cleaning, where extensive image processing based data is generated regarding surface quality (planarity, scratches, particles). Then a complete assembly process takes place, including handling of the disk by means of a vacuum tool, alignment of the disk vs. the heatsink (parallelism and centering) and final bonding by glueing at a micron-thick adhesive gap.

BRIGHTERWAVE use case:

The BRIGHTERWAVE use case covers a classical fiber-pigtailed laser diode module assembly, where the focus is on manufacturing for a high volume production with emphasis on production speed and yield. The design shall cover low prices at high volume production for optical and mechancial components, aiming for low cost glass or injection moldes plastic optics, as well as injection molded plastic opto-mechanics. The tolerancing of the optical design shall allow for relaxed components and assembly tolerances that enable e.g. passive alignment using mechanical stops.

4 Conclusions

The described assembly process chain model for photonics covers main processes along the integration value chain from components to the finally integrated system. It was shown that partially the process chain covers component technologies, e.g. manufacturing technologies, but mainly incoming inspection and classification, singularization, cleaning and deterministic feeding towards handling. Handling itself is carried out throughout the following process chain and is released only after successful bonding, it covers the component pick-up from the feeding media, its transportation to the assembly area and the secure fixation during alignment and bonding, as well as release after bonding. Alignment then is the most crucial step in photonics assembly, as it directly determines the performance of the system to be integrated. Bonding, being the final assembly process step, is of even importance, as it fixes the alignment position over the lifetime of the photonic system.

Various process parameters and influencing parameters have been discussed, nevertheless they only can represent a partial set of all potential parameters and influencing factors. It's obvious that a majority of parameters can be determined by image capturing and processing throughout the assembly process chain, thus storage and distribution of images towards higher level intelligence is one of the major iQonic approaches for production control.

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